

Analysis of Natural Frequency of Gear Shaft Carrying a Single Rotor

Chandan Shrivastava¹ . H.S.Sahu²

1. Department of Mechanical Engg., MIT Bhopal, India

Abstract: The present work is based on the transverse vibration analysis of a rotating shaft. The natural frequencies and mode shapes of the rotating shaft are determined at various modes. The critical speed and resonance analysis on the response of vibrated rotating shaft are also discussed in this work. The mathematical model for the rotating shaft has been considered first to obtain the generalized equation of the proposed structure in theoretical way. Later, the Finite Element Analysis (FEA) was carried out to validate the proposed theoretical method. Numerical analysis has been carried out to compare the exactness of the two methods and found to be very fine convergent. : Present paper deals with theoretical study of critical speed of shaft carrying single rotor. Every object has its own frequency, called as natural frequency. The measurement of this critical speed and related whirling motion is one of the important problems to be addressed by a design and maintenance engineer. Also the whirling of shaft and its motion comes under the category of self-excited motion i.e. self-excited vibration in which the exciting forces and inducing motion are controlled by the motion itself. When the induced frequency matches with natural frequency, resonance will occur at certain speed, this speed is called as „critical speed“.

I. Introduction

Shaft is a component for transmitting mechanical energy and torque and rotation, generally used to connect different additives of a drive train that can't be related without delay because of distance or the need to allow for relative movement between them. As torque carriers, drive shafts are problem to torsion and shear stress, equal to the distinction between the input torque and the burden. They need to therefore be robust sufficient to endure the strain, whilst keeping off too much extra weight as that would in flip growth their inertia. To allow for variations inside the alignment and distance between the riding and driven components, force shafts regularly comprise one or extra widespread joints, jaw couplings, or rag joints, and now and again a splined joint or prismatic joint. **Chun-Ping Zou et al. (2023)** - This paper proposes a modal synthesis method of lateral vibration analysis for such type of rotor-bearing device. When the proposed method is evolved, the elastic coupling unit is defined as “flexible substructure” that's handled for my part and the alternative parts are partitioned into some substructures which are analyzed by finite element method. **Erik Swanson (2021)** - The purpose of this article is to present a sensible understanding of terminology and conduct based in visualizing how a shaft vibrates, and examining problems that affect vibration. It is hoping that this presentation will assist the non specialist better apprehend what goes on within the machinery, and that the specialist may gain a unique view and/or a few new examples. **F. C. Nelson et al. (2019)** - The analysis of the lateral and tensional motion of spinning rotors is replete with packages of Newton's and Euler's equations. Sometimes the intricacies of these equations overshadow their less difficult bodily meaning. This paper tries to make amends for this by means of explaining the dynamic conduct of spinning rotors without writing any equations. **R. Whalley et al. (2015)** - The multivariable irrational, hyperbolic and circular characteristic, input–output dating for the system, is derived. Arbitrary, geometrical shaft profiling may be accommodated within the analytical

strategies mentioned. Conventional frequency response methods are employed in the dedication of the critical speed condition. Specific studies, incorporating cantilevered rotors with non-linear shaft duration–diameter configurations are exact. The widespread applicability of the procedures outlined is emphasized. **Mohammad Hadi Jalali et al. (2014)** - In this paper, full dynamic evaluation of a high velocity rotor with certain geometrical and mechanical houses is carried out the use of 3D finite detail model, one-dimensional beam-kind model and experimental modal take a look at. Good agreement among the theoretical and experimental effects shows the accuracy of the finite element method. The Campbell diagram, essential speeds, operational deflection shapes, and unbalance response of the rotor are acquired that allows you to completely look into the dynamic conduct of the rotating system. **Ma Jing-min et al. (2013)** - The numerical results calculated by Galerkin method are analyzed to indicate the consequences of ply perspective, taper ratio, and transverse shear deformation on the first herbal frequency and essential rotating pace. The outcomes are in comparison with those received by means of the use of finite element package ANSYS and to be had within the literature the usage of different method. **Xujun Lyu et al. (2010)** - In this paper to emulate the operation of such flywheels on a rotor-AMB take a look at rig we recently constructed. Specifically, the 2 AMBs placed at the 2 ends of the rotor are used as supporting bearings, while the other two placed at the rotor mid span and quarter span are used to emulate the generator negative stiffness and gyroscopic results on the rotor dynamics caused by the flywheel disk. Simulation and experimental outcomes are supplied to expose the effectiveness of the proposed emulation method. **I Crăștiu et al. (2008)** - The purpose of this paper is the development and validation of an impulse excitation method to determine flexural important speeds of a single rotor shaft and multy-rotor shaft. The experimental size of the vibroacoustic response is done through the use of a condenser microphone as a transducer. **I Geonea et al. (2007)** - In this paper it's presented the theoretical,

experimental and numerical simulation of important pace for proper shafts. For this reason, its miles designed a digital version of a test bench for shaft essential speed analysis. The studied shaft is established on bearings and on the middle it has set up a heavy disc. **S.A.A. Hosseini (2009)**:- Using the analysis of harmonic balance, combination resonances of in-extensional simply supported rotating shafts with nonlinearities in curvature and inertia are present. The frequency– response curves are plotted for the first two modes. The effects of mass moment of inertia, eccentricity and external damping coefficient are investigated on the steady state response of the rotating shaft. **O. N. KIRILLOV (2009)**:- this paper deal with an axis-symmetric flexible rotor perturbed by dissipative, conservative and non-conservative positional forces originated at the contact with the anisotropic stator. The Campbell diagram of the unperturbed system is a mesh-like structure in the frequency–speed plane with double Eigen frequencies at the nodes.

METHODOLOGY

The procedure for solving the problem is

- Modeling of the geometry.
- Meshing of the domain.
- Defining the input parameters.
- Simulation of domain.

Figure 1.: CAD Model of constant diameter Shaft
Boundary condition and Loading

The boundary conditions applied to the finite element model is as follows.

- The Bearing support parallel to the cross-section of shaft.
- Angular velocity of 3000 rad/s is applied on the cross section shaft.
- **Solution**
- In this step victimization finite component technique by ANSYS 15.0to solve the matter for the outlined material properties, boundaries conditions and mesh size.
- **Post-Processing**

- For viewing and interpretation of results of on top of solved downside. The result will be viewed in numerous formats graph, value, animation etc.
- **Definition of different modes**
- Mode -1 (Backward Whirling) – mode one represents a magnitude of frequency with respect to shaft rotation in unbalanced masses condition.
- Mode -2 (Forward Whirling) - mode two represents a magnitude of frequency with respect to shaft rotation in balanced masses condition.
- Mode -3 (Backward Whirling) - mode three represents a magnitude of frequency with respect to shaft rotation in unbalanced masses condition.
- Mode -4 (Forward Whirling) - mode four represents a magnitude of frequency with respect to shaft rotation in balanced masses condition.
- Mode -5 (Backward Whirling) - mode five represents a magnitude of frequency with respect to shaft rotation in unbalanced masses condition.
- Mode -6 (Forward Whirling) - mode six represents a magnitude of frequency with respect to shaft rotation in balanced masses condition.
- Mode -7 (Forward Whirling) - mode seven represents a magnitude of frequency with respect to shaft rotation in balanced masses condition.
- Mode -8 (Backward Whirling) - mode eight represents a magnitude of frequency with respect to shaft rotation in unbalanced masses condition.
- Mode -9 (Forward Whirling) - mode nine represents a magnitude of frequency with respect to shaft rotation in balanced masses condition.

Figure 2.: CAD model of Shaft with boundary condition

Figure 3: Validation of Frequency and rotational velocity Distributions along the Shaft by Campbell diagram.

Above graph shows the validation result of Campbell diagram with experimental Campbell diagram result of base paper we found that above graph shows convergence with base paper graph, Hence our study is validated.

In this analysis validation is done by using structural steel material and frequency vs. rpm relation was plotted on Campbell diagram at constant angular velocity of 3000 rad/s the convergence values are near to base paper Campbell diagram.

Figure 4.: First modes frequency of gray cast iron shaft of constant diameter

Figure 5: Second mode frequency of gray cast iron shaft of constant diameter

Figure 6.: Sixth mode frequency of gray cast iron shaft of constant diameter

The current analysis presents a study of natural frequency characteristics of a shaft of different profiles. The modal analysis was carried out on Gray cast iron, Stainless steel, Structural steel and Titanium alloy system. The effect of diameter with different profiles of the Shaft with diameter 70-100 mm and 80-100 mm on the natural frequency and modes of different materials and critical speed effects were analyzed on different profile and materials of shaft and

distribution along the shaft was studied. From the analysis of the results, following conclusions can be drawn.

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